

ACUTE FLARES OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS B (AFOCHB): A SMALL REVIEW

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Abstract

Acute flares of chronic hepatitis B (AFOCHB) is defined as an acute disease characterized by sudden rise of levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) five times higher than the upper limit of normal values in a patient suffering from chronic hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection. It can occur in association various disorders and represents a serious condition which requires immediate treatment in order to avoid serious complications, even lethal. This review summarizes the advances in diagnosis and treatment of Acute flares of chronic hepatitis B, AFOCHB.

Keywords: Liver Disease, Chronic Hepatitis B, Treatment ,Virus and Patients.

Introduction

Acute flares of chronic hepatitis B (AFOCHB) is defined as an acute disorder characterized by sudden accretion of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) values up to more than 5 times the upper limit of normal values in a patient affected with chronic HBV virus infection (Chang et al.,2012). AFOCHB occurs in association with various circumstances and clinical comorbidities, such as during or after administration of antiviral therapy or in patients affected with iatrogenic immunosuppression or receiving chemotherapy, due to acute hepatitis A virus infection, in pregnant women, but also spontaneously (in the most of cases) (Chang et al.,2012). (Lok et al.,1991). (Giles et al.,2015). AFOCHB may also be diagnosed in patients affected with liver cirrhosis, with higher risk of worse prognosis and outcome, in fact they can require immediate administration of antiviral therapy, while non –cirrhotic can be clinically followed for some months before deciding to treat them (Chang et al.,2012).

Epidemiology and Etiology

Most of the diagnosed flares cannot be explained by contemporary overlapped viral infections able to cause a liver damage; instead it can be generated by a modification in the equilibrium between immunologic responses against HBV and the amount of viral proliferation; consequently, clinical manifestations can vary from full asymptomatic patient to acute hepatitis and liver failure (Holmes et al.,2017).

In a Greek study, spontaneous reactivation was present in about 27% of cases who received diagnosis of acute hepatitis cases in “carriers” patients (hepatitis B surface antigen – HbsAg positive) with an estimated mortality rate of 18% (Tasso Poulos *et al.*,1987). Some patients may experience multiple episodic hepatitis B flares during life course, while 10%–30% of hepatitis B carrier subjects can experience annually many episodes (Seeff LB and Koff RS 1986). In several previous studies, the risk of hepatic exacerbation development resulted increased both in men and in younger individuals (Perrillo 2001). A positive family history has been also determined as another risk factor for chronic HBV infection when performing differential diagnosis between acute hepatitis B infection and AFOCHB (Perrillo 2001).

A detectable HBV-DNA value at baseline before administrating chemotherapy (with cellular toxicity), the contemporary use of steroids and a previous diagnosis of breast cancer or hematological disorders such as lymphoma can be considered as predictive factors for HBV reactivation (Hung *et al.*,2010). The risk of acute flare seems to be higher in patients with active replication of HBeAg and HBVDNA before undergoing chemotherapy treatment (Hung *et al.*,2010).

In 1991 Lok *et al* reported possible HBV acute flares in 22% of patients with HbsAg positivity and in 2% of subjects presenting anti-HBc and / or anti-HBs positive values with previous diagnosis of malignant lymphoma treated with chemotherapy (Lok *et al.*,1991). Immunosuppression or chemotherapy in patients with chronic or occult HBV infection is associated was considered the trigger factor for reactivation (Lok *et al.*,1991). Some cases of AFOCHB after trans arterial chemoembolization for human hepatocellular carcinoma have also been reported, perhaps due to the impaired liver functional reserve at the time of diagnosis and treatment (Hung *et al.*,2010).

In a recent study involving 140 subjects HBV-infected who had performed renal transplant and are actively monitored, 25% of the patients presented episodes of exacerbation within 3.4 ± 3 years after surgery and variables most associated with exacerbation were the occasional use of prophylactic/preemptive mycophenolate mofetil (MMF) and lamivudine (Eori *et al.*,2014).

Monoclonal antibodies against Cluster of differentiation 20 (anti-CD20) and B cell depletion such as rituximab when added to normal chemotherapy regimen, seemed to increase the risk and severity of AFOCHB even more, also in anti-HBc positive patients and HbsAg-negative and those people carrying combined anti-HBs seropositivity (Huang *et al.*,2013).

Many cases of acute flares have been reported among subjects treated with anti-TNF agents such as etanercept, infliximab adalimumab, which are considered biologic agents approved to treat Crohn disease, ankylosing spondylitis, plaque psoriasis, juvenile idiopathic arthritis, hidradenitis suppurativa, and many other autoimmune disorders, while risk was reduced in patients assuming prophylactic therapy (Cannizzaro *et al.*,2017).

In other cases, superinfection with other hepatotropic viruses can constitute the pathogenetic trigger for development of AFOCHB (es. Hepatitis E. herpes virus, human

immunodeficiency virus), especially during pregnancy or after stressful events (Chang et al.,2012).

Some studies proposed a clear distinction between flares occurring when viral load is stable at the beginning followed by a decrease during time (host induced flares) and virus induced flares, which can be preceded by an increase in viral load which then becomes variable. Patients belonging to the first group seem to have a better response to therapies than the others (Flink et al.,2005).

Pathogenesis

Expanded values of T cells with reactivity against hepatitis B e antigen (HBeAg) and HBcAg that are cross-reactive at the T-cell level seem to mediate acute flares. Increased response of T-cells seems to appear in prodromal phase of flares and reduces after HBeAg seroconversion and recovery from exacerbation (Perrillo 2001).

Pathogenesis of AFOCHB is not completely understood. Previous researches demonstrated an increase of serum HBV DNA, HbsAg, HbeAg, that precedes elevation of ALT weekly to monthly (Liaw YF. H Beag et al.,2009).

A subsequent increase of immune complex formation against anti Hbe and HBeAg/anti-HBe (usually known as immune clearance phase) can constitute the trigger for flares (Liaw et al.,1987). However, they may also occur independently from seroconversion, and these can be considered as abortive attempt (Maruyama et al.,1993 and Liaw et al.,1987). Some patients can experience multiple similar episodes that precede successive flares in the sequent months off course, all these episodes of reactivation and remission can accelerate also the worsening of chronic HBV (Liaw YF. H Beag et al.,2009) (Maruyama et al.,1993), (Liaw et al.,1987).

Before AFOCHB patients can experience a second phase, known as “low replicative”, which is characterized by the presence of anti-HBe high values, quite normal AST values and quite low values of HBV DNA in serum. Liver injury depends on severity of previous damage during the immune clearance phase (Liaw et al.,1988 and Levy et al.,1990).

In patients with previous diagnosis of chronic HBV disorder, hepatitis B acute flares may present during the hepatitis B antigen E (HBeAg) immune phase of clearance (40-50%); less frequently in negative phase, and can be prolonged when clearance of HBeAg seems to be repeatedly unsuccessful (Flink et al.,2005). Hepatitis B flares may also occur during the HBeAg-negative reactive phase (15-30% of patients), but less frequently. It can also present with acute decompensation, and it may be occasionally linked to HBeAg stereovision (Flink et al.,2005).

The immunological changes during acute relapse inflammatory process are very similar to those commonly identified during the course of severe sepsis: exacerbated development of anti-inflammatory cytokines, such as interleukin (IL)-6, interferon-gamma, IL-10, interleukin 12 which can be associated to activation of toll-like receptors (TLR), an and reduced monocyte activation (Chan et al.,2008 and Gao et al.,2011). During AFOCHB

an increased expression due to reactivation of HBV of TLR2/3/4/5/7/9/10 has been observed and IL-17-producing CD4 + T (Th17) cells have both also been involved in the pathogenesis of damage against liver (Chan et al.,2008 and Gao et al.,2011) (24-27). Accumulation of immunoglobulin (Ig)M and IgG targeting the core hepatitis B virus in the liver tissue has been found in patient requiring liver transplantation, such as increased expression of peripheral glucocorticoid receptor expression (Chan et al.,2008 and Gao et al.,2011).

Clinical Manifestations and Diagnosis

The clinical spectrum of hepatitis B flares is very heterogeneous, ranging from totally asymptomatic subjects to patients with mild symptoms such as fatigue, nausea, anorexia, malaise, abdominal pain up to symptomatic ones with acute hepatitis mimicking features (around 30%), characterized by extreme manifestations of severe flares which can present as complications of hepatic decompensation (with serious symptoms and sign such as jaundice and coagulopathy) or even leading to potentially lethal hepatic failure (Bestas et al.,2021).

Bestas and Yalcin found, in almost 60% of evaluated patients, a statistically relevant proportion of jaundice as the first presenting sign. This means that that more than 50% of patients diagnosed with acute hepatic flares can experience acute icteric attacks. Coexistent hepato-splenomegaly have also been found in many previous case series (Bestas et al.,2021).

(Kumar et al.,2003) found similar values of biochemical parameters in acute hepatitis and relapse (transaminases, gamma-glutamyl transferase, lactate dehydrogenase, alkaline phosphatase levels, such as prolonged prothrombin time). Consequently, up to date no serum markers can be used for diagnosis of AFOCHB.

Alpha-Fetoprotein (AFP) is a plasma glycoprotein mainly produced by the intestine, fetal yolk sac and liver. After birth, its production is almost totally repressed and the serum concentration usually decreases to < 20 ng/mL. AFP usually rises due to hepatocellular carcinoma; however high levels have also been found in patients with AFOCHB (Park et al.,2015). Therefore, significant rise of alpha-fetoprotein levels can be both indicative for the presence of a hidden tumor but also can reflect hepatitis disease activity (Yoon et al.,2016). Liver biopsies performed in patients affected with hepatitis B flares show usually lobular necrotic inflammation changes, which may be so relevant that interlobular necrosis or “bridging hepatic necrosis (BHN)” may occur (Chang et al.,2012). This event can occur especially in patients with AFP value > 100 ng/mL during hepatitis B flares compared with 4–5.6% in patients with APF values <100 ng/ml (Park et al.,2015).

In the early phases rising in serum HBV DNA, followed by an increase of both AST and ALT values, such as a possible rising of Anti-HBc IgM, a blood exam which is generally used as a diagnostic marker for acute hepatitis B, can be found in affected patients (Oliveri et al.,2008). IgM anti-HBc may be detectable in both acute and AFOCHB ((Oliveri et al.,2008). They have been object in almost 3/4 of patients experiencing reactivation episodes, even if usually in low titers. (Oliveri et al.,2008).

Previous studies evaluated dynamic evaluation of Liver stiffness measurement (LSM) by transient elastography but, in patients with severe acute exacerbation, it might overestimate the presence of fibrosis while it can misdiagnose liver cirrhosis. Liver biopsy can help to evaluate chronic hepatitis histological pattern, however in may not be possible in patients with coagulopathy or decompensation (Bonino et al.,2003).

In case of hepatitis B flares, not worsened with acute failure or mortality, ALT may decrease to previous levels in about one month (Chan et al.,2000). In HBeAg-positive patients less than 20% of these phases subside later than 3 months, but in the 30% of HBeAg-negative patients it can be followed by persistently raised value of ALT (Huang et al.,2013). Another study revealed that subjects with AFOCHB developed a spontaneous HBeAg sero-clearance rate >50%, and >60% respectively during follow up after 12 and 18-month from flare (Chu 1997).

Hepatitis B infection carriers should always be vaccinated against hepatitis A vaccination, and, especially if affected by chronic HBV, they should be advised to be strictly compliant with proposed treatments; instead those candidates to immunosuppressive treatment should always be evaluated in order to exclude a possible presence of subclinical HBV infection and, if positive, antiviral should be started before immunosuppression.

Mortality in AFOCHB patients was highest within the first 60 days. The severity of the hepatitis flare and a pre-existing underlying liver disease can be considered the two most important risk factors for liver damage (Chang et al.,2012).

The MELD (Model for End-stage Liver Disease) score is a scoring system prospectively developed for evaluating three months survival among patients suffering from chronic liver disease. This model is based on a patient's laboratory evaluation involving serum bilirubin, serum creatinine, and the international normalized ratio (INR) for prothrombin time (Liang et al.,2021).

In a recent study involving 452 patients Liang et al found a worse prognosis (90 day and survival rate after one year) in patients with AFOCHB due to HBV relapse or HAV superinfection compared to the others, while mortality at 28 days resulted the same for two groups.

References

- Bestas, R., & Yalcin, K. (2021). Clinical and Virological Features of Acute Hepatic Exacerbations in Patients With Chronic Hepatitis B Virus Infection. *Cureus*, 13(6).
- Bonino, F., & Brunetto, M. R. (2003). Chronic hepatitis B e antigen (HBeAg) negative, anti-HBe positive hepatitis B: an overview. *Journal of hepatology*, 39, 160-163.
- Bortolotti, F., Cadrobbi, P., Crivellaro, C., Guido, M., Rugge, M., Noventa, F., ... & Realdi, G. (1990). Long-term outcome of chronic type B hepatitis in patients who acquire hepatitis B virus infection in childhood. *Gastroenterology*, 99(3), 805-810.

- Cannizzaro, M. V., Franceschini, C., Esposito, M., Bianchi, L., & Giunta, A. (2017). Hepatitis B reactivation in psoriasis patients treated with anti-TNF agents: prevention and management. *Psoriasis: Targets and Therapy*, 35-40.
- Chan, H. L. Y., Hui, Y., Leung, N. W. Y., Ching, J. Y. L., Chan, F. K. L., & Sung, J. J. Y. (2000). Risk factors for active liver disease in HBeAg-negative chronic hepatitis B virus-infected patients. *The American journal of gastroenterology*, 95(12), 3547-3551.
- Chang, M. L., & Liaw, Y. F. (2014). Hepatitis B flares in chronic hepatitis B: pathogenesis, natural course, and management. *Journal of hepatology*, 61(6), 1407-1417.
- Chronic Hepatitis B patients. *Clinical Immunology*, 128(3), 400-408.
- CHU, C. M., & LIAW, Y. F. (1997). Natural history of chronic hepatitis B virus infection: an immunopathological study. *Journal of gastroenterology and hepatology*, 12(9-10), S218-S222.
- Emori CT, Perez RM, Matos CA, Uehara SN, Pereira Pda S, Feldner (2014) Acute exacerbation of chronic hepatitis B virus infection in renal transplant patients. *Braz J Infect Dis*.18 (6):625-30
- Flink, H. J., Sprengers, D., Hansen, B. E., van Zonneveld, M., De Man, R. A., Schalm, S. W., & Janssen, H. L. A. (2005). Flares in chronic hepatitis B patients induced by the host or the virus? Relation to treatment response during Peg-interferon α -2b therapy. *Gut*, 54(11), 1604-1609.
- Gao, L., Wang, J. F., Xiang, M., Fan, Y. C., Zhang, Z. G., & Wang, K. (2011). Expression of human glucocorticoid receptor in T lymphocytes in acute-on-chronic hepatitis B liver failure. *Digestive diseases and sciences*, 56, 2605-2612.
- Giles, M., Visvanathan, K., Lewin, S., Bowden, S., Locarnini, S., Spelman, T., & Sasadeusz, J. (2015). Clinical and virological predictors of hepatic flares in pregnant women with chronic hepatitis B. *Gut*, 64(11), 1810-1815.
- Holmes, J. A., Yu, M. L., & Chung, R. T. (2017). Hepatitis B reactivation during or after direct acting antiviral therapy—implication for susceptible individuals. *Expert opinion on drug safety*, 16 (6), 651-672.
- Huang, Y. H., Hsiao, L. T., Hong, Y. C., Chiou, T. J., Yu, Y. B., Gau, J. P., & Lee, S. D. (2013). Randomized controlled trial of entecavir prophylaxis for rituximab-associated hepatitis B virus reactivation in patients with lymphoma and resolved hepatitis B. *J Clin Oncol*, 31 (22), 2765-2772.
- Hung, H. H., Su, C. W., Wu, J. C., & Lee, S. D. (2010). Reactivation of hepatitis B virus after transarterial chemo-embolization for hepatocellular carcinoma in one patient with negative hepatitis B surface antigen. *Journal of hepatology*, 52(3), 463-465.

- Kumar, M., Chauhan, R., Gupta, N., Hissar, S., Sakhuja, P., & Sarin, S. K. (2009). Spontaneous increases in alanine aminotransferase levels in asymptomatic chronic hepatitis B virus-infected patients. *Gastroenterology*, *136*(4), 1272-1280.
- Liang, J., Liu, L., Cao, Y., Zhang, Q., Liu, F., Chen, Y., ... & Han, T. (2021). Hepatitis B-related acute-on-chronic liver failure induced by hepatotropic viral insult is associated with worse prognosis than that induced by non-virus insult. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, *21*(1), 1-12.
- Liaw, Y. F. (2009). HBeAg seroconversion as an important end point in the treatment of chronic hepatitis B. *Hepatology international*, *3*, 425-433.
- Liaw, Y. F., Pao, C. C., & Chu, C. M. (1988). Changes of serum HBV-DNA in relation to serum transaminase level during acute exacerbation in patients with chronic type B hepatitis. *Liver*, *8*(4), 231-235.
- Liaw, Y. F., Tai, D. I., Chu, C. M., Pao, C. C., & Chen, T. J. (1987). Acute exacerbation in chronic type B hepatitis: comparison between HBeAg and antibody-positive patients. *Hepatology*, *7*(1), 20-23.
- Lok, A. S., Liang, R. H., Chiu, E. K., Wong, K. L., Chan, T. K., & Todd, D. (1991). Reactivation of hepatitis B virus replication in patients receiving cytotoxic therapy: report of a prospective study. *Gastroenterology*, *100* (1), 182-188.
- Maruyama, T., McLachlan, A., Iino, S., Koike, K., Kurokawa, K., & Milich, D. R. (1993). The serology of chronic hepatitis B infection revisited. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, *91*(6), 2586-2595.
- Oliveri, F., Coco, B., Ciccorossi, P., Colombatto, P., Romagnoli, V., Cherubini, B., ... & Brunetto, M. R. (2008). Liver stiffness in the hepatitis B virus carrier: a non-invasive marker of liver disease influenced by the pattern of transaminases. *World journal of gastroenterology: WJG*, *14*(40), 6154.
- Park, J. W., Kwak, K. M., Kim, S. E., Jang, M. K., Kim, D. J., Lee, M. S., ... & Park, C. K. (2015). Differentiation of acute and chronic hepatitis B in IgM anti-HBc positive patients. *World Journal of Gastroenterology: WJG*, *21*(13), 3953.
- Perrillo, R. P. (2001). Acute flares in chronic hepatitis B: the natural and unnatural history of an immunologically mediated liver disease. *Gastroenterology*, *120* (4), 1009-1022.
- Seeff, L. B., & Koff, R. S. (1986, February). Evolving concepts of the clinical and serologic consequences of hepatitis B virus infection. In *Seminars in liver disease* (Vol. 6, No. 01, pp. 11-22). © 1986 by Thieme Medical Publishers, Inc.. (Seeff LB and Koff RS 1986)
- Tassopoulos, N. C., Papaevangelou, G. J., Sjogren, M. H., Roumeliotou-karayannis, A., Gerin, J. L., & Purcell, R. H. (1987). Natural history of acute hepatitis B surface antigen-positive hepatitis in Greek adults. *Gastroenterology*, *92* (6), 1844-1850.

- Wang, K., Liu, H., He, Y., Chen, T., Yang, Y., Niu, Y., ... & Zhao, Y. (2010). Correlation of TLR1-10 expression in peripheral blood mononuclear cells with chronic hepatitis B and chronic hepatitis B-related liver failure. *Human immunology*, *71*(10), 950-956.
- Yeo, W., Zee, B., Zhong, S., Chan, P. K. S., Wong, W. L., Ho, W. M., & Johnson, P. (2004). Comprehensive analysis of risk factors associating with Hepatitis B virus (HBV) reactivation in cancer patients undergoing cytotoxic chemotherapy. *British Journal of Cancer*, *90* (7), 1306-1311.
- Yoon, Y. M., Kang, D. Y., Kim, D. Y., Seo, J. W., Lim, H. J., Lee, H. J., & Park, S. G. (2016). Extremely elevated alpha-fetoprotein due to acute exacerbation of chronic hepatitis B without malignancy: a case report. *Journal of Medical Case Reports*, *10*(1), 1-4.

